

Long and Short Term Characteristics of a Model of Online Process Control with Inspection Errors and Degrees of Conformity

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Abstract

In online process control an item (or items) is periodically selected for inspection and based on a judgment about whether that item is conforming the decision about whether to declare the process out of control is made. The picture becomes more complicated when the model takes account of the possibility that degrees of conformity can be distinguished and that items can be misclassified and thus multiple classifications are made before a judgment is reached about the conformity of the item. Various protocols for reaching a judgment after multiple classifications can be proposed. We study one such model and look at some long term and short terms properties of the process.

Key Words: Acceptance sampling, Misclassification, Quality

1. Introduction

In on-line process control by attributes items are periodically inspected and the process is stopped for possible adjustment when a nonconforming item is detected. When in control the process is assumed to have some high fraction of conforming items, will we denote this by p_1 . At some point the process shifts to a lower fraction $p_2 (< p_1)$ of conforming items. This has been studied by Taguchi, Elsayed, and Hsiang(1989) and Taguchi, Chowdhury, and Wu (2004).

Nayebpour and Woodall (1993) assume that the random time until the shift is a geometric distribution and thus the attributes of the items produced are modeled as independent and identically distributed trials with a constant probability π for each item to be the first item produced after the shift of the fraction conforming. Since items are only periodically inspected, the first item produced after the shift may not be inspected and therefore there can be number of items produced before it is possible to detect a shift.

Borges, Ho, and Turnes (2001) allow misclassification errors. Let p_{CN} be the probability that a conforming item is judged to be nonconforming and p_{NC} be the probability that a nonconforming item is judged to be conforming. Likewise, we use p_{CC} (p_{NN}) to represent the correct classification of a conforming (nonconforming) item as conforming (nonconforming). Therefore, repeated classifications are made until a final judgement is made. When an item has been judged in this final determination to be nonconforming, the process is judged out of control and is stopped for adjustment. It is also possible that the process is declared out of control when it is not. However, in such a case, no cause can be found and the process then is restarted. It is also possible that the process goes out of control without detection and remains until this is detected at a later time.

Various protocols for deciding whether a process is in control have been proposed and studied. Griffith and Smith (2021) studied a protocol which they called CCTN in which the process was judged to be in control if and only if k consecutive conforming classifications occurred before f nonconforming classifications. The methods developed in that paper can be used as a framework to study other models with appropriate modifications. Griffith and Smith (2018) investigated a protocol in which the final determination that an item is conforming, i.e., the process is in control,

if and only if k total classifications as conforming occur before a total of f classifications as nonconforming and referred to this rule by the acronym TCTN.

Griffith and Smith (2013) studied the TCTN rule in a multistate model in which items are not simply conforming or nonconforming. This current paper extends results in that paper to study the short term and long term behavior of the model. Items produced are superior, acceptable, or unacceptable. When the process is in control, the percentages are p_1, p_2 , and $1 - p_1 - p_2$ respectively and when the process is out of control, the percentages are p_1^*, p_2^* , and $1 - p_1^* - p_2^* (> 1 - p_1 - p_2)$. The process of inspecting an item is subject to possible misclassification. An item which is superior could be judged to be only acceptable or even possibly unacceptable. In similar ways, misclassifications can occur for an item which is actually acceptable or unacceptable. They let p_{ss}, p_{sa} , and p_{su} be the respective probabilities that an item which is superior is judged to be superior, acceptable, and unacceptable respectively. For acceptable items, p_{as}, p_{aa} , and p_{au} they denoted these probabilities and for unacceptable items, p_{us}, p_{ua} , and p_{uu} will represent these probabilities. Every h^{th} item is inspected repeatedly and the process is judged to be in control if and only if either l total items are classified as superior or k total items are classified as either superior or acceptable prior to f items being classified as unacceptable. They called this rule the $TC_1TC_{12}TN$ rule. They let v be the probability that the inspected item is judged superior and ρ be the probability that the inspected item is judged as acceptable and used the notation $TC_1TC_{12}TN(v, \rho)$ to represent the probability that there are l total items classified as superior or k total items as superior or acceptable prior to f classified as unacceptable. The method for calculation of this probability for a given v and ρ will be described later in this paper using a Markov chain approach. Although some of the results in this paper have appeared in Griffith & Smith (2013), we have included them for completeness. New results appear in sections 3 and 4. This paper is devoted to a significant extension of the results in that paper by obtaining both short term and long term results.

2. Markov Chain Analysis

Consider the Markov Chain $\{X_n\}$ with state space $\{(r, s, t): 0 \leq r \leq l, 0 \leq s \leq k, r \leq s, 0 \leq t < f\} \cup \{(0, 0, f)\}$ where $X_n = (r, s, t)$ means that after the n^{th} classification there are r total superior classifications, s total superior or acceptable classifications, and a total of t nonconforming classifications. Let v be the probability of superior classification and ρ be the probability of an acceptable classification.

The transition probabilities are of the form

- $P(X_n = (r + 1, s + 1, t) | X_{(n-1)} = (r, s, t)) = v$,
- $P(X_n = (r, s + 1, t) | X_{(n-1)} = (r, s, t)) = \rho$,
- $P(X_n = (\underline{r}, s, t + 1) | X_{(n-1)} = (r, s, t)) = 1 - (v + \rho)$

Using this information and the recognition that the absorbing states are the states such that $r = l, s = k$, or $t = f$ we can easily determine the one-step probability matrix \mathbf{P} which is described as follows.

For each Markov chain there are absorbing (recurrent) states, which correspond to the end of the repetitive classifications for a single item and the consequent decision.

- Let A denote the set of absorbing states and a denote the number of absorbing states.
- Let T denote the remaining states which are transient and t denote the number of transient states.
- One-step transition probability matrix \mathbf{P} for the Markov chain in canonical form is $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_1 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{Q} \end{bmatrix}$,
- \mathbf{P}_1 is the $a \times a$ identity matrix for the absorbing states
- \mathbf{R} is a $t \times a$ matrix containing the one-step probabilities of the transient states to the recurrent (absorbing) states
- \mathbf{Q} is a $t \times t$ matrix containing the one-step probabilities among the transient states
- $\mathbf{0}$ is the $a \times t$ zero matrix

- The one-step probabilities of \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{Q} are determined by the transition probabilities given for each test. The first row of \mathbf{Q} contains the one step transition probabilities from state $(0,0,0)$.

To compute the moments of the decision time, we will define the following notation. Since elements of T appear as subscripts, we will use i and j as typical elements of T . However, it should be noted that when we do so, each of i and j refer to an ordered pair such as (r,s,t) .

Let,

- $\mathbf{I}_{t \times t}$ = identity matrix of dimension $t \times t$
- $\mathbf{M}_{t \times t} = (\mathbf{I}_{t \times t} - \mathbf{Q}_{t \times t})^{-1}$ - the fundamental matrix of dimension $t \times t$
- \mathbf{e}_m = column vector of length t where the m^{th} element is one and the remaining elements are zero.
- \mathbf{e}_m' is defined to be the transpose of \mathbf{e}_m
- $\mathbf{u}_{\{NS\}}$ = column vector where all the elements corresponding to the nonconforming states are one, and the remainder of the elements are zero.
- $\mathbf{1}_z$ = column vector of ones of length z
- N_{ij} = random variable that represents the number of times the process visits state j before it eventually enters a recurrent state, having initially started from state i ($i, j \in T$).
- $\mu_{ij} = E(N_{ij})$ for $i, j \in T$.
- $\mathbf{M}_\rho = [\sum_{j \in T} \mu_{ij}] = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{1}_t$ - column vector such that the m^{th} element is the sum of the m^{th} row of \mathbf{M}
- $\mathbf{M}_{\rho^2} = [(\sum_{j \in T} \mu_{ij})^2] = \text{diag}(\mathbf{M}_\rho)\mathbf{M}_\rho$ - column vector such that the m^{th} element is the square of the sum of the m^{th} row of \mathbf{M} . Note: $\text{diag}(\mathbf{M}_\rho)$ is a diagonal matrix whose entries are the corresponding entries of \mathbf{M}_ρ .

The results in propositions 1-9 are given without proof and based on formulas in Bhat (1984).

Let $TC_1TC_{12}TN(v,\rho)$ represent the probability that there are l total items classified as superior or k total items as superior or acceptable prior to f classified as nonconforming.

Proposition 1: If the item being inspected is superior (acceptable, or nonconforming), the probability that the process is judged to be in control is

- $P(\text{judged in control} | \text{superior}) = TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{ss}, p_{sa})$.
- $P(\text{judged in control} | \text{acceptable}) = TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{as}, p_{aa})$.
- $P(\text{judged in control} | \text{nonconforming}) = TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{ns}, p_{na})$.

where $TC_1TC_{12}TN(v,\rho) = 1 - \mathbf{e}_1' \mathbf{M} \mathbf{R} \mathbf{u}_{\{NS\}}$

Proposition 2: If the process is in control, the probability that it is judged to be in control is

$$P_{II} = P(\text{judged in control} | \text{in control}) = p_1 TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{ss}, p_{sa}) + p_2 TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{as}, p_{aa}) + (1 - p_1 - p_2) TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{ns}, p_{na})$$

Proposition 3: If the process is out of control, the probability that it is judged to be in control is

$$P_{OI} = P(\text{judged in control} | \text{out of control}) = p_1^* TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{ss}, p_{sa}) + p_2^* TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{as}, p_{aa}) + (1 - p_1^* - p_2^*) TC_1TC_{12}TN(p_{ns}, p_{na})$$

Proposition 4: When the process is out of control, the average run length is $\frac{1}{1-P_{OI}}$.

Proposition 5: When the process is in control, the average run length is $\frac{1}{1-P_{II}}$.

The next four propositions allow the practitioner to find probability mass function and moments of the number of classifications needed for a judgment, for the cases when the process is in control and out of control given the item inspected is superior. What if the item is acceptable? What is the item is nonconforming? When the practitioner is deciding on what criteria to use, these quantities help to determine the optimal parameters for the TC₁TC₁₂TN protocol.

Proposition 6: Let Y be the number of classifications until a judgment is reached. Then the mean, variance, and probability mass function given the item being classified is superior are given as where $(v, \rho) = (p_{ss}, p_{sa})$.

- $E(\text{Decision time} | \text{superior}) = \mathbf{e}_1' \mathbf{M} \mathbf{1}_t$
- $\text{Var}(\text{Decision time} | \text{superior}) = \mathbf{e}_1' [(2\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{M}_\rho - \mathbf{M}_{\rho^2}]$
- $P(\text{Decision time} = m | \text{superior}) = \mathbf{e}_1' \mathbf{Q}^{m-1} \mathbf{R}$

Proposition 7: Let Y be the number of classifications until a judgment is reached. Then the mean, variance, and probability mass function given the item being classified is acceptable are given as where $(v, \rho) = (p_{as}, p_{aa})$.

- $E(\text{Decision time} | \text{acceptable}) = \mathbf{e}_1' \mathbf{M} \mathbf{1}_t$
- $\text{Var}(\text{Decision time} | \text{acceptable}) = \mathbf{e}_1' [(2\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{M}_\rho - \mathbf{M}_{\rho^2}]$
- $P(\text{Decision time} = m | \text{acceptable}) = \mathbf{e}_1' \mathbf{Q}^{m-1} \mathbf{R} \mathbf{1}_a$

Proposition 8: Let Y be the number of classifications until a judgment is reached. Then the mean, variance, and probability mass function given the item being classified nonconforming are given as where $(v, \rho) = (p_{ns}, p_{na})$.

- $E(\text{Decision time} | \text{nonconforming}) = \mathbf{e}_1' \mathbf{M} \mathbf{1}_t$
- $\text{Var}(\text{Decision time} | \text{nonconforming}) = \mathbf{e}_1' [(2\mathbf{M} - \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{M}_\rho - \mathbf{M}_{\rho^2}]$
- $P(\text{Decision time} = m | \text{nonconforming}) = \mathbf{e}_1' \mathbf{Q}^{m-1} \mathbf{R} \mathbf{1}_a$

Proposition 9: Let Y be the number of classifications until a judgment is reached. Given that the process is actually in control (out of control) then the mean is given below.

- $E(\text{Decision time} | \text{in control}) = p_1 E(\text{Decision time} | \text{superior}) + p_2 E(\text{Decision time} | \text{acceptable}) + (1 - p_1 - p_2) \cdot E(\text{Decision time} | \text{nonconforming})$
- $E(\text{Decision time} | \text{out of control}) = p^* E(\text{Decision time} | \text{superior}) + p^{*2} E(\text{Decision time} | \text{acceptable}) + (1 - p^* - p^{*2}) E(\text{Decision time} | \text{nonconforming})$

3. Short Term Analysis Using Markov Chains

In this section we examine the process from the time that is put back in control or started until the next time that it is declared out of control. In Griffith and Smith (2018) Markov chain methodology was used to study this short-term behavior of the process for the TCTN protocol. Appropriate modifications to this approach can be used in the multi-state case. We use a Markov Chain whose state space consists of four ordered-pairs whose elements are one or zeros. We use a 1 to stand for in control and a 0 to stand for out of control. The first coordinate is the actual state of the process and second coordinate is the judgment. As an example, (1,1) means that at a decision point the process is in control and judged to be in control. Whereas, (0,1) means that the process is actually out of control but judged to be in control. If $\theta = 1 - (1 - \pi)^h$ then $1 - \theta = (1 - \pi)^h$ is the probability that the process has remained in control while those h items have been produced. The one-step probability matrix for the transitions of this Markov chain is given in the following transition matrix.

$$\begin{matrix}
& \begin{matrix} (1,1) & (0,1) & (1,0) & (0,0) \end{matrix} \\
\begin{matrix} (1,1) \\ (0,1) \\ (1,0) \\ (0,0) \end{matrix} & \left(\begin{matrix} (1-\theta)P_{II} & \theta P_{OI} & (1-\theta)P_{IO} & \theta P_{OO} \\ 0 & P_{OI} & 0 & 1-P_{OI} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{matrix} \right)
\end{matrix}$$

First-passage probabilities can be calculated to obtain the probability of first reaching each absorbing state in n steps. Adding these probabilities allow us to obtain the probability that the process is declared out of control on the n th item inspected. We can use first-step analysis to find the probability of absorption into (1,0) and into (0,0). Note: $P_{IO} = 1 - P_{II}$ and $P_{OO} = 1 - P_{OI}$. The mean time until absorption will be the mean number of items inspected when the process is declared out of control. Since it is possible that the process can go out of control and mistakenly judged to be in control, we can also find the conditional distribution of the number of times that the process is judged to be in control before we detect that it has gone out of control.

4. Long Term Analysis Using Markov Chains

Griffith and Smith (2018) used Markov chains to study the long-term behavior of the process control in which the TCTN protocol is used. Modifications can be used with the protocol discussed in this article. The process is judged out of control whenever we reach either state (1,0) or state (0,0). When the cause is found and corrected or when it is determined that the process is actually in control and there is no cause, the process is then put back online and the one step transition probabilities are like those from state (1,1). To analyze the long-term behavior of the process, we can use a one-step transition probability matrix in which the rows in the matrix that correspond to transitions out of (1,0) and (0,0) are identical to those out of state (1,1). The one-step transition probability matrix used for long term analysis is given below.

$$\begin{matrix}
& \begin{matrix} (1,1) & (0,1) & (1,0) & (0,0) \end{matrix} \\
\begin{matrix} (1,1) \\ (0,1) \\ (1,0) \\ (0,0) \end{matrix} & \left(\begin{matrix} (1-\theta)P_{II} & \theta P_{OI} & (1-\theta)P_{IO} & \theta P_{OO} \\ 0 & P_{OI} & 0 & 1-P_{OI} \\ (1-\theta)P_{II} & \theta P_{OI} & (1-\theta)P_{IO} & \theta P_{OO} \\ (1-\theta)P_{II} & \theta P_{OI} & (1-\theta)P_{IO} & \theta P_{OO} \end{matrix} \right)
\end{matrix}$$

Since this is a one-step transition probability matrix of an irreducible, aperiodic, positive recurrent Markov chain the limiting probabilities exist and are independent of the starting state. These limiting probabilities can be interpreted as the long-term proportion of time spent in each state and can be computed by solving a system of linear equations.

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